

Influence of Classroom Control and Management on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Enugu East Local Government Area

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of effective classroom control and management on the academic performance of secondary school students in Enugu East LGA. The study was guided by one specific purpose and one research question. From a population of 36,711 a sample size of 335, were drawn using simple random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire which was validated by experts was used to collect data for the study. The reliability of the instrument was carried out using Cronbach's Alpha and this yielded a reliability index of 0.75. The data collected was analyzed using mean score. The result showed that use of the right teaching methods and adequate use of instructional material helps in improving classroom management and control in secondary schools. The researchers recommended that workshops/seminars should be organized for teachers on the importance of instructional materials in teaching and learning process so as to improve their classroom management.

Keywords: Classroom Management, Classroom Control, and Academic Performance

Introduction

Classroom management has been highlighted across numerous research studies as a major variable that affects students' academic performance. The most obvious reason for this assertion is that, effective classroom management sets the stage for teaching and learning. It sets a tone in the classroom that captures students' attention – as a necessity for effective teaching and learning (Onyali, 2020). This statement is obvious since a classroom which is chaotic and disorganized as a result of poor classroom management is highly unlikely to enhance expansive learning and students' academic performance and might, indeed, inhibit it. In chaos, according to Ononye (2020), very little academic learning can take place. According to Walter (2012), classroom management differs from one teacher to another because of the teacher's personality, teaching

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style, preparedness, and number of students in the classroom. According to Oguejiofor (2020), the concept of classroom management is broader than the notion of student control and discipline, it includes all the things teachers must do in the classroom to foster students' academic involvement and cooperation in classroom activities to create conducive learning environment.

Nwankwo (2022), relates that classroom management involves curtailing learner's disruptive behaviors such as fighting and noise making, close observation, arrangement of classroom learning materials, and response to students who suffer from poor sight (vision), poor hearing, poor reading, poor writing, poor spelling, shame, dullness, hyperactivity and poor study habits. When classroom management is viewed in a more wider and holistic sense, incorporating every element of the classroom from lesson delivery to classroom environment becomes important ('Obiakor' 2022). According to Nicholas, this includes creating organized and orderly classroom, establishing expectations, inducing students' cooperation in learning tasks, and dealing with the procedural demands of the classroom. This view of classroom management contrasts to a more narrow view of classroom management as it deals with just discipline and control. According to Bassey (2012), the wider view of classroom management shows increased engagement, reduction in inappropriate and disruptive behaviors, promotion of student responsibility for academic work, and improved academic performance of students. In effect, discipline, control and the consequences become authoritative or punitive approaches to classroom management. These have become much smaller part of the term classroom management. Thus, classroom management denotes much more than any of these words (Charlie, 2016).

In the view of Williams (2014), classroom management involves how the teacher works, how the class works, how the teacher and students work together and how teaching and learning takes place. An analyses of the past 50 years of classroom management research identified classroom management as the most important factor, even above students' aptitude, affecting students' learning and academic performance (Akubilo, 2019). Contrary to popular belief held by Obi and Obiakor (2021), classroom management is not a gift bestowed upon some teachers. While it is true that some teachers adapt to classroom management easily, making it felt by their colleagues as if they possess some innate talents. Classroom management is a skill that can be acquired like any other profession. It is a skill that must be practiced to achieve proficiency. Classroom management thus requires specific skills such as planning organizing, as well as an aptitude for team work. It requires a great deal of commitment, initiatives, teachers' willingness to adjust, creative thinking and actions (Abel, 2011)

Ofojebe and Obiakor (2022) observes that improved teacher training in classroom management is a critical part in improving academic performance in a particular subject. Factors contributing to effective classroom management include: teaching methodology, lesson planning and preparation, interpersonal relationships and student motivation (Gaston, Lee and MacArthur 2010). Ezenwagu and Obiakor (2021) observed that structuring a classroom so that it supports positive student behavior requires prior planning. The structure of the classroom environment should decrease the likelihood of inappropriate student behavior and increases desirable student

interactions and consequently improves academic performance. A classroom environment would enable learners to study in a way that is interesting, enjoyable and purposeful. Among models to restructure a good classroom environment include: use of a variety of teaching methods and involving students to numerous learning activities, physical class arrangement that allows a teacher to access students, efficient use of class time and ensuring that students interact positively during cooperative learning activities (Obiakor and Oguejofor, 2021). Kerr and Nelson (2012) assert that the use of rules is a “powerful, preventive component of classroom organization and management plans.” Rules are aimed at establishing the expected behaviors, what to be reinforced and the consequences for inappropriate behavior. Thus emphasis of effective class discipline helps to cut down on discipline problems and leave the classroom with fewer interruptions and disruptions. Wong (2009) believes that student performance is influenced by how well the procedures are laid out and taught to them.

To instill class discipline, teachers should introduce class rules early enough when the year is beginning and make sure they are understood by all. The teacher should be fair and impartial across all the students. In case of disruption within a lesson, the teacher should deal with the interruption with as little distraction as possible. Teachers should consider over planning as a recipe to avoid giving students free-time within the lesson. The teacher should be consistent in that they cannot afford to ignore negative behavior. Collins (2012) advocates for “cooperative discipline” where the teacher and students work together to make decisions. To him teachers should come up with a code of conduct that shows how students should behave and not how they should not behave. This instills discipline in a child as they know what is expected of them. Glenn (2013) emphasized the need for teachers to hold class meetings severally. Class meetings encourage respect among teacher and students. According to Barbara Coloroso theory of Inner self control, students should be given an opportunity to develop their self-control and that classrooms are the ideal places for this opportunities.

Thus class discipline can be identified through the use of lesson plans, learning activities, a code of conduct (rules and routines), communicating to parents and through group works (Collins 2012). Consequently there are strategies that promote good use of routines such as: praising, giving a token and signing behavior contracts with students with behavior problems (Emmer and Stough 2011). In South Africa: school Act of 1996 encouraged the need for positive disciplinary strategies as opposed to corporal punishment. Mabeba and Prinsobo (2010) asserts that positive discipline builds a learners’ self-esteem and enables them to cooperate and participate in the classroom and consequently assume responsibility for what happens. A research carried out by Nelson (2012) in Nigeria shows that teachers who assist students to set high expectations and engage them in self-evaluation of their performance get better grades as compared to student with poor self-efficacy.

Kerr and Nelson (2012) encourage the use of humor as a way to engage students and activate their learning. To them, when teachers share a laugh or a smile with students, they help students feel more comfortable and open to learning. Moreover, humor brings enthusiasm, positive feelings, and optimism to the classroom. Teachers are expected to conduct a needs analysis to identify the needs of students so as to capture their attention during learning process. Students need to be taught respect for self and others so that they can be able to function healthily in the

society (Rogers, 2009). In Nigeria, as a behavior adjustment strategy, guiding and counseling department has been introduced in educational institutions as opposed to corporal punishment used in many African countries. Thus a good classroom environment should promote independent learning (Kireria 2014). Students should be exposed to numerous learning activities so that they can take pride in their accomplishments and instill a desire for knowledge.

The quality of education has been reflected not only in the subjects taught and achievement levels reached, but also in the learning environment. The environment has both reflected and influenced the behavior of students, and it has been affected by events within and outside of the school (Condition of Education, 2014). Most educators and researchers have agreed that the total environment should be comfortable, pleasant, and psychologically uplifting; should provide a physical setting that students find educationally stimulating; should produce a feeling of well-being among its occupants; and should support the academic process. One major aspect of the classroom climate that has fallen under the control of the teacher is that of classroom management and discipline. As might be expected classroom climate which motivated learning and afforded the students the opportunity to be actively and meaningfully engaged in academic activities influenced the positive rating of teacher's classroom management hence the relation to their performance in physics.

Classroom management has referred to all the planned or spontaneous activities and interactions that have occurred within a classroom. In recent years, a growing interest has emerged in the area of classroom management. The classroom environment is a large part of classroom management that will either encourage students to succeed, or hamper their abilities and cause more failures. The classroom environment is different than the classroom management because it deals with how the students feel in the classroom. While classroom management focuses on procedures, routines, and expectations, the classroom environment focuses on the relationships between students and teachers, as well as how the students feel amongst their peers in the classroom (Stepanek, 2011). Classroom management is the heart of teaching and learning in school setting. A well-managed classroom can provide an exciting and dynamic experience for everyone involved. Unfortunately, student behavior can often with this process. Good classroom management implies not only that the teacher has elicited the cooperation of the student s in minimizing misconduct and can intervene effectively when misconduct occurs, but also that worthwhile academic activities are occurring more or less continuously and that the classroom management system as a whole is designed to maximize student engagement in those activities, not merely to minimize misconduct. Many times, by encouraging behavior that is more positive and uplifting in one classroom, the behavior will carry on into other classrooms, taking the safe environment further than one classroom. Student achievement, as well as emotional and social outcomes, can all be positively affected by a safe, positive learning environment (Stepanek, 2011). When teachers do not tolerate disrespect both among students and between the students and teacher, they set the standard for their classroom and students feel more encouraged to participate and take risks in the classroom. Because of this, setting the classroom environment is often just as important as establishing classroom management strategies.

Teachers have entered a new age of classroom management. Faced with new challenges during the first part of the twenty first century teachers, teacher educators and school administrators have searched for alternative ways to manage classrooms. However, finding answers to classroom management situations is difficult because there is disagreement about what constitutes effective classroom management approaches.

Some administrators and teachers think of classroom management and discipline as being synonymous terms. Vasa (2014) describe classroom management as behaviors related to maintenance of on-task student behaviors and the reduction off-task or disruptive behaviors. Those who share his view define effective classroom management as a way of preparing students for life. They focus not on controlling students' behavior today but on preparing students for the world they live in tomorrow. Teachers and administrators who approach classroom management from this perspective define effective classroom management as the process of creating a positive social and emotional climate in the classroom (Morris, 2016). One of the most important skills possessed by effective teachers is that of classroom management. These skills are considered by Lang (2012) as by far the most important aspect of a teachers training and they state that effective classroom management is largely concerned with disruptive strategies, but other aspects are also of vital importance. Aspects are also of vital importance. The definitions developed by Conrath (2011) for classroom management includes the organization and planning of students' space, time and materials so that instruction and learning actives can take place effectively.

Alternatively, effective classroom management was divided into four main categories in the studies of Evertson & Emmer (2012) and Sanford (2014). These four categories are: classroom procedures and rules, student work procedures, managing student behavior and organizing instruction. It is clear from these examples that classroom management is much more than a collection of strategies for discipline and involves many aspects of a teacher's professional expertise. Teacher's varying approaches to classroom management are reflected in differing levels of effectiveness. For example, a well-prepared teacher has a much greater chance of achieving effective lesson management. In the discussion of Lang (2012), different approaches to discipline are said to range from intimidation to total permissiveness. They advise that such extremes should include monitoring and enforcing reasonable classroom rules, procedures and routines. Effective teaching is more than discipline alone and classroom management has been closely linked to the achievement and engagement of high school science students (McGarity & Butts, 2010). Both this study and the discussion of Lang indicate that teachers should strive to develop effective classroom management techniques and that this will have a significant impact on their educational effectiveness. An analysis of the past fifty years of educational research as noted by (Wang, Haertel, and Walberg 2011) revealed that effective classroom management increases student engagement, decreases disruptive behaviors, and makes good use of instructional time.

A teacher is a person who possess specified knowledge and skills from an institution of higher education and have fulfilled requirements for certification (McNergney and Herbert 2011). Teacher qualifications include attaining a post graduate certificate in education (PGCE),

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Professional Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) and Bachelor of Education. Telia (2013) defined teacher qualification as the highest educational certificate possessed by a particular teacher. Whitehurst (2009), views teacher qualification indicators as; teacher's academic ability, teacher's certification status, teacher's instructional practice in the classroom, teacher's subject matter expertise and experience. In the study area, teacher preparation takes the form of undergraduate training with a period of teaching practice designed to provide opportunities to practice in the classroom. During teaching practice, the trainee is required to maintain a record about students' needs and abilities, classroom rules and routines and the flow of instructional activities. At the same time, the trainee is expected to conduct tutoring sessions in the classroom or/and assist the teacher with classroom activities. It is after successful completion of the five year undergraduate course that a teacher is awarded a certificate or licensed if they meet the basic requirements and standards of a particular state.

Moreover, the certification is a way of preventing harmful teaching practice. Thus the certified teacher needs to continually attend seminars organized in colleges and university campus to discuss issues of teaching and share ideas about more and less effective teaching strategies. In a research carried out by Moreau (2017), asserts that extra training of teachers influences pupil learning outcomes positively. Extra training improves teacher performance by sharpening both their technical skills and their instructional competence.

This is confirmed by the fact that many state governments in Nigeria have increased the requirements for one to qualify for certification (MacPhialWilcox and King 2012). At the same time, it was noted that possession of master's degree or teacher education at graduate level did not have an impact on pupil learning. However, Bidwell and Kasadra (2009) asserted that teacher qualification is closely tied to teaching skills that is the nature of instruction and concluded that teacher retention in the profession was of significant importance in influencing the level of student performance. Goldhaber and Brewer (2010) noted significant achievement on high school students handled by teachers with standard, probationary or emergency certification as compared to those students handled by teachers who are not certified and those who held private school certification. Similarly, Fetler (2009) found that students of fully certified teachers did better than those of emergency certified teachers. In India there are two groups of teachers; teachers with formal Education (TFEs) and subject specialist teachers. The TFEs are teachers with minimum qualification in Bachelor of Education degree or Masters in Education but they are not subject specialists. Specialist teachers include teachers with at least a Master's degree in a particular subject.

In conclusion, teacher training should provide appropriate field experience. The trainees should practice with experienced teachers in their subject field (Emmer and Stough, 2011). They recommend that teacher training programs should provide content and supervised experience related to classroom organization and behavior management.

Poorly managed classrooms are usually characterized by disruptive behaviors such as sleeping, late coming, noise making, miscopying of notes, eating, calling of nicknames, verbal or physical threat to fellow students or the teacher (Ekere, 2013). These disruptive behaviors disorganize

learning processes and hamper academic performance of students. Effiong (2012) suggests that teachers can deal with these disruptive behaviors in the classroom and reduce them to the minimum through effective classroom management so that effective learning can take place. Once teachers are able to effectively reduce or eliminate disruptive behaviors in the classroom, there would be increased academic attentiveness and engagement which would pave way for better academic performance by students. The use of verbal instruction is one of the techniques for effective classroom management that can be adopted by teachers. According to Good (2014), clear instruction on what should be done gives the students concrete direction to compliance. In this approach, teachers try to be consistent in enforcing the verbal instruction so that it produces the desired results. Until recently, corporal punishments were used widely as an effective classroom management technique to curb disruptive behaviors in the classroom. It is now not commonly applicable through it is still practiced in some schools as an effective classroom management technique.

Instructional supervision is another technique of effective classroom management adopted by teachers in the classroom. According to Obot (2010), instructional supervision involves moving around the classroom to observe students closely, engaging students in academic activities, asking questions and employing both verbal and non-verbal teaching methods to ensure that students are paying undivided attention and taking more from the lesson than simple facts. Delegation of authority to learners is still another technique of effective classroom management where the teacher delegates his/her authority to deserving students and assign them duties such as cleaning chalk board, time keeping, controlling noisemakers, managing learning materials, collecting assignment from students, copying lesson notes on the chalk board, class representatives on behalf of the class (Nima, 2014). These contribute a great deal to making the classroom a conducive place since cooperation between students and teachers in the classroom is fostered. Classroom management techniques are aimed at producing conducive learning environment where students can learn with ease and perform better academically. All of these techniques can be adopted in the classroom depending on the nature of the problem at hand. This study is aimed at examining the influence of effective classroom control and management on the academic performance of secondary school students in economics in Enugu East LGA.

Statement of the Problems

Unconducive learning environment in the public schools has posed serious problems to students' academic performance over many decades ago. This trend has been on the increase on daily basis. Its prevalence has attracted the concern of the teachers, parents, the guidance counselors and many researchers. Effective classroom management has been discussed extensively at educational seminars and workshops, with efforts aimed at bringing lasting solution to the problem of students' poor academic performance encountered in secondary schools. In most cases, classroom teachers become tired of using verbal instruction in attempts to establish effective classroom management, but this method alone does not produce desired results. Many teachers use corporal punishment to instill fear and discipline in the classroom yet there are prevalence of disruptive behaviors in the classroom. A lot of teachers waste time and energy in intensive classroom supervision so that the classroom climate could be conducive for lessons.

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Some classroom teachers delegates authority to deserving prefects such as time – keeper, noise prefects, class prefects, etc. to share in the responsibility of ensuring a conducive learning atmosphere in the classroom. These methods are adopted by teachers to enable the classroom become conducive enough for effective teaching – learning process and to facilitate higher academic performance of the students and it seems not to be yielding any result hence this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the influence of effective classroom control and management on the academic performance of secondary school students in economics in Enugu East LGA of Enugu State.

Research Question

How does the environment influence classroom management and control in secondary schools?

Methods

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which was carried out in public secondary schools in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State. One research question guided the study. From a population of 38,077 respondents, a sample of 335 was drawn using a multistage sampling procedure. A researchers’ developed instrument titled “Classroom Management and Control Questionnaire” (CMCQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach’s Alpha and this yielded reliability coefficient of 0.75. The instrument was considered reliable in line with Nworgu (2015), who stated that if the co-efficient obtained for an instrument is up to 0.70 and above, the instrument should be considered good enough to be used for a study. The direct administration and retrieval method was used for data collection. Mean was used to answer the research questions.

Results

Table 1: Mean responses of respondents on how environment influences classroom management and control in secondary schools

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Home factor/parental upbringing affects the child behavior in school	2.61	.83	Agree
2	Unfriendly school atmosphere influences classroom management	2.86	.98	Agree
3	Lack of teacher’s attention in the school influences classroom management	2.65	1.28	Agree
4	Inadequate infrastructure influences	2.50	1.16	Agree

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5	classroom management Influence of peer groups affects classroom management and control	2.56	.95	Agree
6	Children from wealthy single parent homes do not have much financial support compared to their counterpart from poor single parent's homes.	2.66	1.23	Agree
7	Children from poor parental homes do not have much financial support compared to those from wealthy single parental homes.	2.52	1.28	Agree

According to the table above, the respondents agree that all seven items are factors that influence classroom management and control in secondary schools in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State. The mean ratings for the seven items ranged from 2.50 to 2.86.

Discussion

The finding of the study showed that unfriendly school atmosphere, inadequate infrastructure, influence of peer groups and lack of teacher's attention in the school are some of the environmental influences on classroom management and control in secondary schools. This was in line with the findings of Johnson (2013) who noted that uncondusive learning environment and non-availability of the teaching materials can make the teaching/learning environment boring and unbearable. Also, the finding Ngwangwa (2012) is in line with the findings of the present study. His study showed that environmental influences impacts on teachers' classroom management and control.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that unfriendly school atmosphere, lack of teacher's attention in the school, peer group influence and inadequate infrastructure influences classroom management and control in secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that;

- i. Schools should endeavor to provide the necessary learning facilities that will enhance classroom management and control.
- ii. Teachers should be advised to use the available instructional material in teaching as it will enhance their classroom management

References

- Adeqive, P. W. (2012): *Classroom Assessment*. New York: Mc Grant Hill.
Alausa, A. (2018): *Introduction to Research in Education*. Wadsworth. Thomson Learning. Nek Publishers.

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Copyright © authors 2023

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- Ango, P. (2010): Formative and Summative Assessment Teacher studies in Service education.
- Dahiru, W. (2011): Observing Activities. London: Paul Champman.
- Denga, P. (2011): Mauritia; Continuous Assessment Still only on Paper. Port Louis, L'express.
- Dodo, S.A. (2013): Continuous Assessment in Nigeria Senior Secondary School Geography: problems and implementation strategies. A Paper Presented at the Annual Conference of the International Association for educational Assessment at the NCON- Hilton Hotel Abuja Nigeria Sept 4-8, 2013
- Eze J. U, Oguejiofor, C N, Nnadi Ursula U, & Obiakor, M. Impact Of Nursery Education On The Academic Performance Of Primary School Pupils In Enugu East Local Government Area Of Enugu State
- Ezewu, J. H and Okoye, M. (2012). Strategic Planning At Afrcian Universities: "How Relevant are Northern Models?" Higher Education Policy.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2012)
- Federal Ministry of Education (2014)
- Finkelstein, V. (2011). Using Assessment to improve the quality of Education Paris: UNESCO International Institute for Education Planning.
- Hall, T.N. (2013): "Appraising the Use of CA among Primary School Teachers." Paper Presented at the International conference on Problems and Prospects of Primary Education in Nigeria and Other Developing Countries, May 1985 University of Nigeria.
- Idowu, T, and Esere, V. (2011): Monitoring Performance: Assessment and Examination in Africa. Washington DC World Bank.
- Ijaya, M. (2012): Policy and Practice in Assessment in Anglophone Africa. Does globalization explain convergence? Assessment in Education.
- Killaghan, F, and Greany, T. (2011). Outcome Evaluation. In D.L. Stufflebeam, G.f. Madaus &
- Ngwangwa, C. A. (2012). Classroom management styles of secondary school teachers and students' discipline in Orlu Education Zone of Imo State. (Unpublished master's thesis). Imo State University, Nigeria.
- Obiakor M.I & Oguejiofor C. N (2020) Impact of Classroom Size on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria[PDF] from ajemates.org
- Oche, M (2012) Commodifying Learning; Pitfalls and Possibilities; Reflection on Higher Education University of Bath UK
- Oguneye, P. (2012): Teaching Methods across the curriculum. Worcester; Billing and Sons Ltd, UK.
- Okwudili, M.B (2009) Educational Measurement and evaluation. Lagos Longman.
- Ola, B. (2010): Feedback as a Poor Performance Remediation. A Report Submitted for Publication in Journal of education, University of Calabar, 2010 Nigeria.
- Ononye, F. & Obiakor M.I (2020) 20222023 Factors Responsible for Mass Failures in Economics in senior secondary Schools (Ssce) Examination in Enugu Educational Zone. *UNIZIK Journal of Educational Research and Policy ...*, 2020

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Copyright © authors 2023

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- Onyali, L. (2020) Lessons from around the World. How Policies, Politics and Cultures Constrain and afford Assessment Practices. *The Curriculum Journal* 16(2) 249-261
- Walter A. (2012): Improving Students' Performance through Feedback Mechanism in Secondary Schools. Ibadan, University of Ibadan.
- Oyesola, A. (2010), Idowu, T and Esere, V (2009): Continuous Assessment as an Instrument of Achieving Learning Objectives. Unpublished Research Report, Ibadan, University of Ibadan.
- Plessis, M and Prouty, C. (2009): Assessing Achievement in the Arts. Buckingham, Open University Press.
- Quanash, R. J (2015): Students- Centered Classroom Assessment. New York Merrill/Macmillan.
- Richard, J. (2010): Basics of Qualitative Research; Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory. SAGE Publication. Thousand Oaks London New Delhi.
- T. Kellaghan (Eds.), Evaluation Models, Viewpoints on Educational and Human Services Evaluation Boston. Kluwer Academic.